
**IMPACT OF NON-FORMAL EDUCATION PROGRAMMES ON WOMEN
EMPOWERMENT FOR COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT IN ORLU AND
ORSU, IMO STATE**

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Abstract

The study examined the impact of non-formal education programmes on women's empowerment for community development in Orlu and Orsu Local Government Areas of Imo State. Three research questions, and one null hypothesis guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey design with a population of 969 women participants in adult and non-formal education centres in the area of study. The sample size of 524 respondents was selected using a proportionate sampling technique and the research instrument was a self-structured questionnaire titled "Impact of Non-Formal Education Programmes on Women Empowerment Questionnaire" (INEPWEQ). The statistical tools used for data analysis were percentage, mean, and z-test. A reliability coefficient of 0.73 was obtained using Cronbach alpha method. The findings of the study revealed that literacy education has equipped women with reading, writing and numeracy skills; enabled them to know their fundamental human rights; ignited their interest and motivation to learn new things; improved their participation in decision making processes in their families and various communities. Also, the finding revealed that vocational education has enabled women to secure new employment or careers; increased their income earning chances; made them self-reliant and independent; and reduced their poverty level. The findings further disclosed that health education has enabled women to adequately maintain good sanitation, increased their awareness of disease prevention and other related health issues, improved their knowledge on maternal mortality, and builds their family's nutrition. The study recommended among others that state and local government authorities should adequately provide funds meant for the non-formal education sector.

Keywords: Non-Formal Education, Literacy Education, Vocational Training, Health Education, Women Empowerment, and Community Development

Introduction

Community development (CD) programmes or projects emanate from an individual's abilities to identify needs and aim towards solving the known needs. CD is the "employment of community structures to address social needs and empower groups of people" (Mendes, 2008:250). Community development underlines empowerment, equality, social justice, participation, and representation as key devices (Amakye, 2017). Correspondingly, Oyebamiji and Adekola (2008) outline the tools of community development as participation, empowerment, self-help, mobilization, and communication. The Igbo socio-cultural environment reduces womanhood and exposes them to their male counterpart. Among the Igbos of Imo State for instance, women cannot hold authoritarian positions in their communities, they lack the right to ownership of properties, and cannot acquire a landed property unless they did so in their son's or husband's name, not allowed to break kola nut whether a man is present or not, anticipated to marry early and they face certain cruel traditional practices harmful to their health such as genital mutilation and widowhood rituals (Odimewu & Okemgbo, 2003). Duru, Diwe, Uwakwe, Merenu, Emerole, Aguocha and Iwu (2016:2) pointed out common harmful cultural practices affecting women in the Orlu Local Government Area and the socio-demographic factors influencing this act. Among the practices include dowry price practices, education deprivation, and female genital mutilation while the socio-demographic factors include marital status, educational level, age perimeter, duration in marriage, household and family size, and living with other individuals. The above revealed that women were marginalised in their various communities. Women's impact on community development was given support by Jackson in Okemini and Chukwuemeka (2011:121) "there are significant inequalities in access to productive resources which prevent women in developing countries and Nigeria in particular from utilizing their potentialities in community development and sometimes, even from meeting their basic needs".

Nigerian women are restricted by culture which makes them defenceless, unprotected, and weak to effectively join the workforce and contribute their quota to community and national development (Ifedili & Ifedili, 2012). These unfavourable practices have squelched the expected successful impact on community development in the Orlu and Orsu Local Government Areas (LGAs) of Imo State. In Nigeria, the consciousness about women's concerns as regards community development gained recognition around the 1980s. This was encouraged by the involvement of Nigerian women in a conference at the international level (Eades in Olaleye, 2011:166). Noticeable among the conferences include the UN 1975 Conference in Mexico, the UN 1980 Conference in Copenhagen in Denmark, the UN 1985 Conference in Nairobi in Kenya, and the UN 1995 Beijing Conference in China. These conferences sprang up non-governmental organizations by Nigerian women to empower themselves.

Ovute, Dibia and Obasi (2015) identified a few governmental and non-governmental organizations including; the National Council of Women Societies (NCWS), the National Women Commission (NWC), Country Women Association of Nigeria (COWAN), Women in Nigeria (WIN). The government also supported women empowerment programmes through former and present first ladies. They are the Better Life Programme for Rural Women by Maryam Babangida, Women Rights Advancement and Protection Alternative (WRAPA) by Mrs. Lami Abubakar, the Child Care Trust by Stella Obasanjo, the Women and Youth Empowerment Foundation (WAFOT) by Mrs. Turai Yar'Adua, (Arum, 2010). Worthy of mention are the Women Summit by Patience Jonathan and the Future Assured Programme by Mrs. Aisha Buhari. Apart from the national efforts, the wife of the previous governor of Imo State Mrs. Nkechinyere Okorochoa in partnership with the United Nations Fund for Population

Agency (UNFPA) initiated anti-movement for female genital mutilation with a protest match in which over 500 female students and women drawn from various schools and communities at the state level participated. In addition, she established skill acquisition and economic empowerment centres and collaborated with the New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD) in enhancing women and youth empowerment in Imo State.

The disregard for women's freedom to contribute to CD activities has experienced heavy criticism. According to UNESCO in Nwobi (2013) for a meaningful CD, women who make up a larger number of individuals must be adequately involved. Okemakinde (2014) views women's empowerment as a real mechanism for multiple women's skills and abilities, their authority above the resources, and their decisions upsetting their existence. Women empowerment (WE) which emerged as the solution to women's inequality, molestation, and subordination, gained the required attention through the hard work of non-formal education programmes that took the undertaking of providing women with relevant skills, knowledge, thoughts, and evidence vital for the promotion of community development in Orlu and Orsu Local Government Areas of Imo State.

Historically, non-formal education (NFE) became a piece of an international institutionalized method of reasoning on education between the 1960s and 1970s (Olobube and Egbezor, 2012). They identified four distinguishing features of NFE to include:

1. Relevance to the desires of disadvantaged groups;
2. Concern with specific categories of person;
3. A focus on clearly defined purposes and
4. Flexibility in method and organisation.

The above features affirm that NFE is an organised educational programme that carries people along toward achieving their aim and objectives irrespective of gender, age, status, and occupation. Bada-Nyarko and Zumapkeh (2013) while citing Green perceive the aspirations of NFE to include awareness-raising, building community skills, and capacity of previously excluded, oppressed, exploited, or isolated groups. NFE programmes here include literacy education, vocational education, and health education.

- i. **Literacy Education:** Literacy entails the ability to compute numeracy, read and write. This definition of literacy is not satisfactory because, literacy goes beyond reading, writing and arithmetic to include other numerous skills such as interpreting, communicating, identifying, etc. To address the difficult associated with conceptual clarification of literacy, in Jometien, literacy definition was extended to include basic learning needs and competence (BLNC) in which literacy is seen beyond mastering the 3R's to include other knowledge, life and problem-solving skills (Patrick and Ijah, 2013:110). UNESCO (2015a) defines literacy as:

a key component of adult learning and education. It involves a continuum of learning and proficiency levels which allows citizen to engage in lifelong learning and participate fully in community, workplace and wider society. It includes the ability to read and write, to identify, understand, interpret, create, communicate, and compute, using printed and materials, as well as the ability to solve problems in an increasingly technological and information rich environment.

- ii. **Vocational Education:** Vocational education converse educational training that provides practical know-how in a particular occupational field. Vocational education programme consisted of skills acquisition, professional training, industrial training and on-the-job training. It is commercial, technical or professional in content and knowledge updating in the changing world (Ezimah, 2009). Vocational education was acknowledged as non-formal education programme that could be adopted or employed for women empowerment in various communities for creation of wealth, development of skills and promotion of community development. Ahamad, Sinha and Shatri (2017) asserted that vocational education programme is introduced to improve livelihood opportunities of women, who are neglected, marginalized and have a scant exposure to technical know-how.
- iii. **Health Education:** The term health education has been perceived as an academic discipline with different definition by authorities. Generally, health education is responsible with providing health information to motivate and assist individuals to develop their health status (Achal, Okpako & Ekenedo, 2009). Here, health education is designed to influence women day-to-day decisions on personal and public health. Health literacy is cognitive and societal skills that resolve the motivation of individuals to comprehend and use information in ways that promote and support good health (WHO, 2013). Women health is a critical area of concern that requires adequate attention for the survival of every nation. One area empowerment interventions have targeted is women's health since it is a crucial element in ensuring their personal and community health (Davis, Schensul, Schensul, Verma, Nastasi & Singh, 2014). Similarly, well-being of a country is the health and safety concern of women. Reason being that health is an important instrument in measuring women empowerment (Aneja, 2015).

These programmes were organized by the Department of Adult Education (DAE) in Orlu and Orsu LGAs, and a non-governmental and non-profit making organization named Women of Divine Destiny Initiative (WODDI). DAE offers basic literacy, post-literacy, and functional literacy and WODDI provides women with several vocational and health services on fashion design, catering, cosmetology, hairdressing, computer training, health, and good fortune programmes that address issues concerning the physical, social, and mental health of the women. These programmes erased the barriers behind women's inactive involvement and gave hope to marginalised women in the development initiatives of their various communities. Therefore, this study is an endeavour to discover the impact of NFE programmes on women's empowerment for the promotion of community development in Orlu and Orsu Local Government Areas of Imo State.

Statement of the Problem

In our various communities, women are perceived as the weaker vessels. They are marginalised and oppressed by the opposite gender. They have limited power to initiate and influence community development activities in their societies. Women are denied the right to land ownership, leadership positions and decision-making, etc. in their various kinfolds and communities at large. For women to surmount this oppression, they need to be empowered.

NFE programmes have been realised as a contrivance for WE. These programmes are prepared to inculcate pertinent expertise in the women to support them overcome oppression and marginalisation and contribute profoundly to CD. The NFE programmes that have an impact on WE for the promotion of CD are literacy education, vocational education, and health education and are conducted by DAE and WODDI in Orlu and Orsu LGAs. The problem of

this study is, therefore, to examine the impact of NFE programmes on WE for CD in Orlu and Orsu LGAs of Imo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the impact of literacy education programme on women empowerment for the promotion of community development in the study area?
2. What is the impact of vocational education programme on women empowerment for the promotion of community development in the study area?
3. What is the impact of health education programme on women empowerment for the promotion of community development in the study area?

Hypothesis

The null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between the impact of literacy education programme of Orlu and Orsu Local Governments on women empowerment for the promotion of community development.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey design. According to Nwankwo (2013) descriptive survey is the gathering of data from a large sample drawn from a precise population which describes definite features of the sample as they are, at the time of the study. The population of this study consists of nine hundred and sixty-nine (969) women participants in the 20 registered adult education and empowerment centres in Orlu and Orsu LGAs of Imo State. The sample of the study consist of five hundred and thirty-three (533) women participants in adult education centres in the study area. Proportionate sampling technique was used to select 55% of the total population in the 20 centres above; given us a representative sample size of 533 out of 969 women learners and this was considered adequate for the study. The instrument used for data collection was a twenty-five (25) items structured questionnaire tagged “Impact of Non-Formal Education Programmes on Women Empowerment Questionnaire” (INEPWEQ). The questionnaire was segmented into two parts (Part A and B). Part A sought the opinion of the respondents on their personal background information while part B was structured to elicit a modified 4 – point Likert type scale of responses: Strongly Agree (SA) = 4; Agree (A) = 3; Disagree (D) = 2; and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1.

The researchers administered a total of five hundred and thirty-three (533) copies of questionnaire to the respondents with the help of four research assistants trained on administration of research instrument. Five hundred and twenty-four (524) copies of the questionnaire representing 98.3 per cent were correctly completed and used for the study. Out of five hundred and thirty-three (533) distributed copies of the questionnaire, it was found out that nine (9) copies of the questionnaire representing 1.69 percent were not correctly completed and, therefore, were not used for the study. Internal consistency method was used to get the reliability of the validated instrument. 15 copies of questionnaire were administered to respondents outside the chosen population of the study. Coefficient value of 0.73 was obtained at 0.05 alpha level using Cronbach alpha statistics. Percentage, mean and z-test statistics was used for data analysis. Percentage was used in analysing the demographic information of the respondents; mean was used in analysing the data for answering the research questions while z-test statistics was used in testing the hypothesis. The data were arranged and presented in

tables for clarity. The criterion mean was 2.50. The items with mean of 2.50 and above were considered as affirmative response by the respondents while mean below 2.50 did not agree with the item. i.e. $4 + 3 + 2 + 1 = \frac{10}{4} = 2.5$

Analysis of Demographic Data of Respondents

Table 4.1: Distribution of the Demographic Background of Respondents, Frequency and Percentage

S/N	Demographic Background	Frequency	Percentage
1	Age		
	20-30years	90	17.18%
	31-40years	216	41.22%
	41-50years	180	34.35%
	51 and above	38	7.25%
	Total	524	100%
2	Occupations		
	Farming	139	26.53%
	Trading	232	44.27%
	Civil Servant	153	29.2%
	Total	524	100%
3	Marital Status		
	Married	388	74.05%
	Single	72	13.74%
	Widow	35	6.68%
	Divorced	29	5.53%
	Total	524	100%
4	Educational Qualifications		
	FSLC	140	26.72%
	WAEC/GCE/NECO	171	32.63%
	NCE/OND	138	26.33%
	HND/BSC	75	14.31%
	Total	524	100%
5	Participants of Non-formal Education Centres		
	Non-formal Education Centres in Orlu	334	63.74%
	Non-formal Education Centres in Orsu	190	36.26%
	Total	524	100%

In table 4.1, the data under age demographic show that 90 respondents representing 17.18% were of the ages of 20-30, 216 respondents representing 41.22% were of the ages of 31-40, 180 respondents representing 34.35% were of the ages of 41-50 while 38 respondents representing 7.25% were of the ages of 51 and above.

The data under occupation of the respondents show that 139 respondents representing 26.53% were into farming, 232 respondents representing 44.27% were into trading while 153 respondents representing 29.2% were civil servant. The data under marital status show that 388 respondents representing 74.05% were married, 72 respondents representing 13.74% were

single, 35 respondents representing 6.68% were widows while 29 respondents representing 5.53% were divorced.

The data under educational qualifications show that 126 respondents representing 24.05% were holders of First School Leaving Certificate (FSLC), 171 respondents representing 32.63% were holders of WAEC/GCE/NECO, 138 respondents representing 26.34% were holders of NCE/OND, while 75 respondents representing 14.13% were holders of HND/BSC. The data under participants of programmes centres show that 334 respondents representing 63.74% were participants in Orlu centres while 190 respondents representing 36.26% were participants in Orsu centres.

Analysis of Data on Research Questions

Research Question I: What is the impact of literacy education programme on women empowerment for the promotion of community development in Orlu and Orsu LGAs of Imo State?

Table 4.2: Analysis on the Impact of Literacy Education Programme on Women Empowerment for Promotion of Community Development in the Study Area.

S/N	ITEM	ORLU						ORSU								
		SA 4	A 3	D 2	SD 1	N	\bar{X}	DECISION	SA 4	A 3	D 2	SD 1	N	\bar{X}	DECISION	
1	Literacy education has equipped me with reading, writing, and numeracy skills.	120	111	60	43	334	2.92	Agree	73	64	40	13	190	3.05	Agree	
		480	333	120	43	976			292	192	80	13	577			
2	Literacy education has enabled me to know my fundamental human rights	97	130	75	32	334	2.87	Agree	40	69	50	31	190	2.62	Agree	
		388	390	150	32	960			160	207	100	31	498			
3	Literacy education has ignited my interest and motivation to learn new things	115	87	94	38	334	2.84	Agree	51	45	68	26	190	2.64	Agree	
		460	261	188	38	947			204	135	136	26	501			
4	Literacy education has improved my participation in decision-making in my community	73	109	46	106	334	2.50	Agree	75	53	35	27	190	2.93	Agree	
		292	327	92	106	817			300	159	70	27	556			
5	Literacy education has improved my participation in decision-making in my family	85	124	77	48	334	2.73	Agree	31	56	70	33	190	2.50	Agree	
		340	372	154	48	914			124	168	140	33	465			
Average Mean							2.77	Agree							2.75	Agree

The data in Table 4.2 show that in Orlu LGA the respondents agreed with all the items on the impact of literacy education programme on women empowerment for promotion of community development with mean scores of 2.92, 2.87, 2.84, 2.50, and 2.64 respectively. In Orsu LGA, the data also show that the respondents agreed with all the items on the impact of literacy education programme for the promotion of community development with mean scores of 3.04, 2.62, 2.64, 2.93, and 2.50 respectively.

Based on criterion mean of 2.5 and above, the following are considered as the impact of literacy education programme on women empowerment for promotion of community development in Orlu and Orsu LGAs of Imo State:

- i. Literacy education equips women with reading, writing, and numeracy skills
- ii. Literacy education helps women to know their fundamental human rights
- iii. Literacy education motivates women to learn new things that will help them to promote community development.
- iv. Literacy education also helps to improve the participation of women in the decision-making process in their various communities.
- v. Literacy education helps to improve the participation of women in the decision-making process in their various families.

The average mean of 2.77 and 2.75 confirms the affirmative response of the respondents on the impact of literacy education on women empowerment for the promotion of community development in Orlu and Orsu LGAs of Imo State.

Research Question 2:

What is the impact of vocational education programme on women empowerment for the promotion of community development in the study area?

Table 4.3: Analysis on the Impact of Vocational Education on Women Empowerment for Promotion of Community Development in the Study Area.

S/N	ITEM	ORLU						DECISION	ORSU						DECISION		
		SA 4	A 3	D 2	SD 1	N	\bar{X}		SA 4	A 3	D 2	SD 1	N	\bar{X}			
1	Vocational education has made me self-reliant and independent	133	100	47	54	334	2.93	Agree	52	55	43	40	190	2.63	Agree		
		532	300	94	54	980			208	165	86	40	499				
2	Vocational education has enabled me to seek new employment or careers	125	112	58	39	334	2.97	Agree	76	54	41	19	190	2.98	Agree		
		469	336	116	39	991			304	162	82	19	567				
3	Vocational education has increased my income-earning opportunities.	97	129	75	33	334	2.87	Agree	81	58	30	21	190	3.05	Agree		
		388	387	150	33	958			324	174	60	21	579				
4	Vocational education has reduced income disparities between me and others	46	85	135	68	334	2.33	Disagree	35	62	40	53	190	2.42	Disagree		
		184	255	270	68	777			140	186	80	53	459				
5	Vocational education has reduced my poverty level	67	100	117	50	334	2.55	Agree	61	67	44	18	190	2.90	Agree		
		268	300	234	50	852			244	201	88	18	551				
Average Mean								2.73	Agree							2.79	Agree

The data in Table 4.3 show that in Orlu LGA the respondents disagreed with item 4 of the questionnaire which divulged that vocational education has not reduced income disparities among women. All other items were agreed by the respondents as the impact of vocational

education programme on women empowerment for promotion of community development with mean scores of 2.63, 2.97, 2.87, and 2.55 respectively.

In Orsu LGA, the data show that the respondents agreed with all the items except item 4 of the questionnaire. The agreed responses were divulged with mean scores of 2.63, 2.98, 3.05, and 2.90 respectively. Based on criterion mean of 2.5 and above, the following are considered as the impact of vocational education programme on women empowerment for promotion of community development in Orlu and Orsu LGAs of Imo State:

- i. Vocational education prepares women to be self-reliant and independent
- ii. Vocational education helps women to seek new employment or careers
- iii. Vocational education increases women’s income-earning opportunities.
- iv. Vocational education helps women to reduce their poverty level.

The average mean of 2.73 and 2.79 confirms the affirmative response of the respondents on the impact of vocational education on women empowerment for the promotion of community development in Orlu and Orsu LGAs of Imo State.

Research Question 3: What is the impact of health education programme on women empowerment for the promotion of community development in the area of study?

Table 4.4: Analysis on the Impact of Health Education on Women Empowerment for the Promotion of Community Development in the Study Area.

S/N	ITEM	ORLU							ORSU							
		SA 4	A 3	D 2	SD 1	N	\bar{X}	DECISION	SA 4	A 3	D 2	SD 1	N	\bar{X}	DECISION	
1	Health education has enabled me to adequately maintain good sanitation.	134 536	82 246	55 110	63 63	334 955	2.86	Agree	77 308	52 156	35 70	26 26	190 560	2.95	Agree	
2	Health education has improved my knowledge of maternal mortality.	91 364	128 384	79 158	36 36	334 942	2.82	Agree	66 264	50 150	45 90	29 29	190 533	2.81	Agree	
3	Health education has encouraged me to use available health resources.	56 224	84 252	133 266	61 61	334 803	2.40	Disagree	42 168	38 114	74 148	36 36	190 466	2.50	Agree	
4	Health education has helped me improve my family’s nutrition.	89 356	121 363	69 138	55 55	334 912	2.73	Agree	37 148	68 204	35 70	50 50	190 472	2.50	Agree	
5	Health education has increased my level of awareness of disease prevention and other related health issues.	134 536	103 309	45 90	52 52	334 987	2.96	Agree	53 212	71 213	39 78	27 27	190 530	2.79	Agree	
Average Mean							2.75	Agree	2.69							Agree

The data in Table 4.4 show that in Orlu LGA the respondents disagreed with item 3 which revealed that health education has not encouraged women to use available health resources with a mean score of 2.40. All other items were agreed by the respondents as the impact of health education programme on women empowerment for promotion of community development with mean scores of 2.86, 2.82, 2.73, and 2.96 respectively.

In Orsu LGA, the data show that all the respondents agreed with all the items the on impact of health education programme on women empowerment for promotion of community development with mean scores of 2.95, 2.81, 2.50, 2.50, and 2.79 respectively. Based on a criterion mean of 2.50 and above, the following were considered as the impact of health

education programme on women empowerment for the promotion of community development in Orlu and Orsu LGAs:

- i. Health education enables women to adequately maintain good sanitation
- ii. Health education improves women knowledge of maternal mortality
- iii. Health education helps women to improve their families' nutrition
- iv. Health education increases women's level of awareness of disease prevention and other related health challenges.

Although in Orsu LGA, health education encourages women to use available health resources, while in Orlu LGA health education does not encourage women to use available health resources. The average mean of 2.75 and 2.69 confirms the affirmative response of the respondents on the impact of health education programme on women empowerment for the promotion of community development in Orlu and Orsu LGAs of Imo State.

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the impact of literacy education programme of Orlu and Orsu Local Government on women empowerment for the promotion of community development

Table 4.5: z-test calculation on the impact of literacy education programme of Orlu and Orsu Local Government on women empowerment for the promotion of community development

Categories	N	Mean	Sd	Df	z.cal.	z.crit.	Decision
Orlu women	334	13.8084	2.08508			1.96	Null hypothesis accepted
Orsu women	190	13.6684	2.30035	522	.711		

Table 4.5 revealed that women in Orlu L.G.A have mean and standard deviation scores of 13.8084 and 2.08508 while women in Orsu L.G.A have mean and standard deviation scores of 13.6684 and 2.30035 respectively. With a degree of freedom of 522, the calculated z-test value of 0.77 is less than the critical z-test value. By implication, the null hypothesis was accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the impact of literacy education programme of Orlu and Orsu Local Governments on women empowerment for the promotion of community development in the area of study.

Discussion of Findings

The data analysed in Table 4.2 for answering research question one (1) indicated that the respondents agreed with all the items on the impact of literacy education programme on women empowerment for promotion of community development in Orlu and Orsu LGAs of Imo State. The results exhibited that literacy education programme has equipped women with reading, writing, and numeracy skills, enabled them to know their fundamental human rights, ignited their interest and motivation to learn new things, and improved their input in the decision-making processes in their families and various communities in Orlu and Orsu LGAs of Imo State. The aforementioned results exhibited that literacy education programme has impacted positively on women empowerment for the promotion of community development in Orlu and Orsu LGAs of Imo State. This was in line with the results of Kotsapas (2011) which revealed that a non-formal literacy education programme offers women who missed out on formal school another great opportunity to gain pertinent skills, knowledge, and in addition address their gender needs. Similarly, the discoveries of Nzeh (2012) were in agreement with the present study which revealed that women become literate, respected in their families and

societies, acquire certificates for better jobs, occupy higher leadership positions, overcome inferiority complex, become self-employed and partake actively in decision-making in their communities through participation in literacy education programmes. The results of Olomukoro and Adelere (2015) conform to the present study which disclosed that women partake more actively in political events; decision-making processes and social communication at home; public gatherings and the community at large; and they gain self-assurance and self-esteem through their involvement in the literacy programme.

The data analysed in Table 4.3 for answering research question two (2) specified that the respondents agreed with items 1, 2, 3, and 5 on the impact of vocational education programme on women empowerment for the promotion of CD in Orlu and Orsu LGAs of Imo State. The results exhibited that vocational education has made women self-reliant and independent, enabled them to secure new employment or careers, increased their income-earning chances, and reduced their poverty level. Item 4 of the questionnaire disagreed that vocational education has reduced income disparities between women and others. The summary of the results above specified that the vocational education programme has impacted positively on women empowerment for the promotion of CD in Orlu and Orsu LGAs of Imo State. The results of Olawunmi (2015) were in consonant with the present results which revealed that vocational education programme for women has assisted in raising their economic positions and the opportunity of contributing financially to their family's and community's needs. The results of the World Bank (2012) showed that vocational education programme empowered women to be self-employed, secure employment, and augment their monthly wage earnings. Findings of Garbuja and Pasa (2016) divulged that technical and vocational education played a role in transforming women empowerment and socio-economic development process in the grassroots level.

The data analysed in Table 4.4 for answering research question three (3) specified that the respondents agreed with items 1, 2, 4, and 5 on the impact of health education programme on women empowerment for the promotion of community development in Orlu LGA. However, in Orsu LGA, the respondents agreed with all the items on the impact of health education programme on women empowerment. The results exhibited that the health education programme has enabled women to adequately maintain good sanitation, improved their knowledge of maternal mortality, helped them to build their family's nutrition, and increased their awareness of disease prevention and related health issues. Item 3 of the questionnaire disagreed that health education has encouraged women to use obtainable resources for good health in Orlu LGA. Nevertheless, item 3 of the questionnaire was agreed upon in Orsu LGA. A summary of the above results, apart from item 3 in Orlu LGA, specified that the health education programme has impacted positively on women empowerment for the promotion of community development in Orlu and Orsu LGAs Imo State. The results of this study were in harmony with the results of Abiodun, Olu- Abiodun, Sotunsa and Oluwole (2014) which specified that interventions of health education programme on women have increased their awareness of prevention of diseases and related health issues. The results of Umar, Afolayan, Emmanuel, Rejuaro, Onasoga and Ibitoye (2017) averred that the intervention of health education programme on women has significantly improved their knowledge level about delivery care services.

The data in Table 4.5 for testing hypothesis one divulged that there is no significant difference between the impact of literacy education programme of Orlu and Orsu Local Governments women empowerment for the promotion of community development. The findings of Adekola and Kumbe (2016) further divulged a significant difference between the literate and illiterate women participation in CD.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, succeeding recommendations were made:

1. State and local government authorities should adequately improve their efforts and released funds meant for the growth and development of non-formal education programmes for women empowerment.
2. Government at all levels and non-governmental agencies should frequently organise training for the practitioners in the field of Adult and Non-Formal Education in order to update their skills and knowledge for effective service delivery.
3. Cultural practices which hinder and endanger women's active participation in non-formal education programmes for promotion of community development should be abolished through awareness creation amongst community members.
4. Women organisations and community-based organisations (CBOs) should influence and encourage women to enrol in non-formal education and empowerment programmes designed for them in order to bridge the perceived oppression and marginalisation affecting them in their various communities.
5. Responsible and relevant development agencies and private individuals should support the women with affordable non-formal education programmes to enable them participate energetically in the course of learning.
6. Non-formal education centres should as much as possible withdraws outdated instructional facilities and equipment and brings in sufficient and current instructional materials for effective service delivery.

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